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किं तेन हेमगिरिणा रजताद्रिणा वा
यत्राश्रिताश्च तरवस्तरवस्त एव।
मन्यामहे मलयमेव यदाश्रयेण
कङ्ककोलनिम्बकुटजाः अपि चन्दनाः स्युः ॥

THE QUARTERLY JOURNAL OF INDIAN
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POOR HOUSES – THE FORGOTTEN INSTITUTION

**Kishor Kumar
Ajay Singh**

In the United Kingdom, a poor house was commonly known as a workhouse. But in India, during the famine of 1860-61, the first poor house was established. It was the most important state agency that provided relief to the famine-stricken poor population of the country. The relief distribution in these poor houses was in the form of cooked food rather than grain or cash.

Keywords: Poor Houses, Famine, Relief Work, Caste, Rajtarangini, Arthashastra, Patwaris, Tehsildar

The late nineteenth century was witness to a large number of famines in colonial India. These resulted in a very high mortality rate and created circumstances which aggravated food scarcity in the country. This article discusses the poor houses or the relief houses that were supposed to provide relief from famine. These poor houses were established in some districts of the North West Provinces and in the Awadh region of North India.

In the United Kingdom,¹ a poor house was commonly known as a workhouse. These were institutions where all those who could not support themselves financially were given employment and accommodation. Before the Poor Laws were introduced, each parish had its own workhouse. Often, these were simple farms wherein the occupants spent their time either working on the farm or helping in maintaining the local roads or other Parish works. As has been depicted by Charles Dickens, a workhouse could be either a reformatory where whole families lived or a penal labor regime where manual work was given to the residents as a form of physical punishment.

In the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, poor houses were very common in the United States. Most of them were located on the grounds of a poor farm. These county or town-run residences were supported by the public expense and mainly the elderly or disabled people resided there. Most of these were working farms and residents if their health allowed, had to provide labor, take care of the housekeeping and also look after the other inmates. These working

farms provided some produce, grain, and livestock. The number of these poor houses decreased after the Social Security Act came into existence in 1935 and they disappeared completely by 1950.

In Canada, most of the poor houses had an attached farm. This type of facility, the oldest government-supported facility that still exists, although it has been converted into a museum, is located in Southern Ontario. It was established in 1877 and over the years, supported almost 1500 poor inmates, including destitute, old, infirm, or disabled. In 1892 a hospital was added to the building and in 1947, it was converted into a home for the aged. In 1975, it reopened as the Wellington County Museum and Archives.

During the famine of 1860-61 that the first poor house was established in India. It was the most important state-run agency that provided relief to the poor population. The first poor house was established at Moradabad,² a district in the Rohilkhand region of the North West Province (NWP), by its magistrate John Strachey. This became a prototype that included all the core principles around which other poor houses were modeled.³ This was then adopted throughout the province.

Initially, these poor houses were considered asylums for those who could not receive relief and had run out of other modes of survival, such as vagrants, homeless cripples, beggars, sick people, abandoned old people, or children. The mortality rate in these poor houses was high.

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A major transition noted was the participation of women who left their homes and took recourse to relief works and poor houses. They had to labor along with the males and also compete with them for food. But the relief measures were not only insensitive to the needs of women, they were also discriminated against along gender, caste, and class lines, as could be seen by the distribution of wages. In spite of the discrimination, the harsh conditions, and the manual work which was undertaken by women, a significant feature of the famines of 1860-61, 1868-69 and 1897-98 was the presence of a large number of women and children working on relief works. It was specifically noted in Bundelkhand that on large relief works the number of women and children was much higher than that of men. Calculations show that for every 100 men, there were 306 women and children who received wages. Thus there was only one man to every four or five women and children.⁴

During the famine of 1868-69, in the poor houses at Bijnor women were much more than men.⁵ This could be because the male members of the family migrated or deserted women and children leaving them to fend for themselves. Thus, women of socially so-called inferior castes assumed new roles as carriers, since men usually worked as diggers. The traditional role and division of labor between the two sexes had virtually broken down.

Instead of making special provisions for women, the discrimination in wages only widened by the turn of the twentieth century. This was opposed by some officials during 1837-38, but later this disparity in work wages remained uncontested and became customary and was even given the status of law by the Famine Code of 1880.⁶ Women laborers were treated with contempt and in the local language were referred to as vagrants, 'wretched', 'coolies', or even 'he'. What was worth thinking about was not the high number of women in these relief works, but that these women who were only domesticated made a decision to work as laborers and gain employment so that they could take care of their families and themselves. This was especially noticeable and appreciable because in those times working for wages was socially considered as status-reducing. These women were discriminated against and treated harshly at three levels - by the Indian society, which discriminated according to caste and class lines, by their male counterparts, and by the government officials.

The distribution of relief in the poor houses was in the form of cooked food rather than grain or cash. Arrangements were made for cooking and maintaining sanitation. A conservancy and a dispensary were attached to each poor house. There were elaborate rules for distributing cooked food.

At these poor houses, the concerned officers searched for *Brahmin*, *Thakur*, or *Kayastha* cooks. This was because the Central Relief Committee which was formed in Agra in 1860 ruled that "The food distributed should be cooked by persons ... care being taken that these persons shall be, such as that none would object on the grounds of caste prejudices, to receive food from them."⁷ So much so that at the poor houses in Bareilly and Pilibhit which had almost 5,000 residents each, "Separate blocks were allotted to the *Thakurs*, the *Mohammadans*, and the *Chamars*, etc. The officials also took care that there was no interference with regard to caste prejudices."⁸ This was necessary because the *Saiyyads*, *Pathans*, *Thakurs*, and *Brahmins* would refuse to accept relief not due to their social pride, but because of their reluctance to be shepherded with the low castes.⁹

The poor houses or state kitchens were unpopular even during the famine of 1877-78, wherein between the *Bhangis* and *Chamars*, the two lower castes, the *Chamars* thought themselves to be superior and would object to being placed along with the *Bhangis*. The bureaucrats themselves were caste conscious and strengthened social distinctions of caste and classes to their advantage.

At the same time, these poor houses were considered work houses where all those who were deserving, eligible, or willing to work were offered subsistence. All those who were healthy or able-bodied or seeking assistance were discouraged. But soon the poor houses became unpopular as they were perceived as places that violated caste norms. The discipline in these institutions was very severe and the food was so bad that it could not even be compared to the food in the prisons, it was even worse than that given to animals. But inmates were forced to eat even though they suffered from various ailments and stomach disorders. Some even preferred to die than to submit themselves to the degradation of the poor houses.

Those who could were provided with work

such as sewing, weaving, making ropes or dures or grinding corn for women, while males were given heavy work such as making or repairing roads or building sheds.¹⁰ The harsh conditions and the indignity associated with the poor houses discouraged the needy from availing of relief. There were also a number of rumors about poor houses, one of which stated that if you went there you would be forcibly converted to Christianity.¹¹ In these poor houses, cooked food was served only once in 24 hours and that too without any variation in the foods. The purchase, preparation, and distribution of food was supervised by a subcommittee that consisted of some “respectable members of the Native community, with a trustworthy Government officer e.g., a Deputy Collector or Tehsildar”.¹²

Almost a hundred poor houses had become operational by February 1861 and approximately eighty thousand needy had availed their services. By June, this figure had reached 1.40 lakh.¹³

But it was noted that even until the 1880s people had to cover long distances to reach these poor houses or relief stations. Although a large amount of work was assigned to the inmates here, the physical conditions were difficult, unhygienic, and degrading. The wages provided were very low which could not even take care of the average nutritional needs. But the explanation given was that this was in the spirit of the Poor Laws and was a recourse to the moral economy even during the 1896-97 famine. Often, wages were further reduced because according to the officials starving people would still make use of such facilities as they had no other alternative to saving their lives.

Thus, it was seen that a harsh environment was intentionally created in these poor houses, which some have even compared to 'death traps', which also spread diseases and epidemics, killing thousands in the process.¹⁴ It was also noted that no provision was made for the economically reintegration of the famine victims.

Government officials felt that in some cases, male relatives who were supposed to support their wives and female relatives often forced them to go to the poor houses so that they were relieved of the burden of looking after them.¹⁵ In a number of instances, the males used the excuse of their wives

living at relief camps and poor houses by breaking tradition and divorced them. This was also the fate of Must Nasiban, wife of Chidda, caste Sheikh, and resident of Bhunsia, at Moradabad police station. She was forced to live in the poor house during the 1877-78 famine. But when she came back home, her husband disowned her as she had stayed in the poor house. Feeling dejected and harassed, she tried to commit suicide but was saved. Despite knowing of her situation, the court sentenced her to three months of imprisonment for attempted suicide. Ultimately, she died of gripes in the prison.

Another case was of Hukumia, wife of Chidda, caste Bhangar. To save her life, she had to live in the poor house, but again she was shunned by her husband for living there. Syed Imdad Ali recorded that this was the fate of the majority of women, who went to poor houses to save their lives and made use of the relief facilities.¹⁶ Therefore, it was seen that women were very vulnerable as they were not only under pressure to survive but also under ideological pressure to maintain their honour. Such circumstances left them emotionally and psychologically scarred.

The Deputy Collector of Moradabad, Syed Imdad AH, brought to the notice all how relief at the poor houses was manipulated and money was being usurped. He alleged that "the enormous sums of government money are nominally spent on public charity, but in reality, they are embezzled by dishonest persons engaged in management".¹⁷ It was very tempting for the officials to make a profit by siphoning off the money meant for wages and selling the grain. Mostly, good grain was sold to the local *Bania* and merchants for a substantial profit. One of the contemporary journals noted during 1837-38: "The relief society feeds about 1500 daily, but then owing to the villainy of those who serve food, the flour is so adulterated with lime and sand that heaps upon heaps have died on eating it".¹⁸

During the four famines, the *Patwaris* and *Tehsildars* were the ones who misused the funds and by 1896-97, the name *Patwari* was considered synonymous with oppression and corruption. The press even alleged that some of the *Patwaris* became rich through these means and relief did not reach the needy.

Although the poor houses were unpopular and

had a number of shortcomings, they were still the backbone of the relief provided to those suffering from famine. Their usefulness and justification were summarised by the 1901 Commission as: 'The poor houses cost little; they can do no harm, and they may atone for a time or altogether the necessity for more extensive and costly measures of relief.'¹⁹

So, even though the poor houses were unpopular, the colonial administration continued to run them, and they ultimately became an important part of the state-sponsored gratuitous relief. The government was aware of the dislike for the poor houses, but they were convinced that some of the locals were used to the free support from people ruling them.

For instance, between March and August 1869, in the Ajmer division a large number of *Marwaris* came to the poor houses. They refused to do any kind of work saying that they had come to be fed by the government and not to work.²⁰ Henvey's report did not agree with this because as per him "it was not the custom of native states to demand labour from starving paupers". He believed that such kinds of people expected alms/allowances? from their government and not wages.

An important theme for discussion during the ancient and medieval literature of India was also about how the rulers were to act and behave during natural calamities such as famines. History also tells us that even the precolonial rulers thought it their duty to provide relief during such times. An ideal monarch was obligated to provide relief during famines. According to Kautilya's *Arthashastra*, a king's moral duty was to maintain the faith of the people and, if needed, he should provide seed and food from his resources as well as from the rich. The common man should also be provided with employment through public works. Even wealth should be redistributed and the government should assist the people to migrate to areas not facing famine.²¹ Kalhan's *Rajtarangini* also gives details of the methods that were adopted to counteract the effects of the Kashmir famine in 917-18 AD.

Accounts for medieval and Mughal India discusses the measures that were taken to fight famine. Ala-ud-Din Khilji, Muhammad-bin-Tughluq, Akbar, Shahjehan and Aurangzeb took various steps to provide relief to the common man during famine.

In the late thirteenth century, Ala-ud-Din Khilji had issued regulations regarding famine. Some of which were the establishment of grain stores in every locality of the capital city, rationing grain at fixed prices and opening free kitchens.²² This has been considered the closest to a logical relief policy.

There were several severe famines during the reign of Muhammad-bin-Tughluq. The measures adopted by him to provide relief included the transfer of his capital and the population from Delhi to Devnagiri. This is considered one of the best examples of state-sponsored migration. But this proved to be counterproductive, resulting in heavy loss of life and immense suffering. Tughluq's positive relief measures included advancing loans to farmers, sinking wells, encouraging migration, and distribution of free rations to the population of Delhi at the rate of twelve *chittacks* per day. He also established charity houses where free cooked food was distributed to the needy.²³

Similarly, the Mughal emperors opened alms-houses and free kitchens, which also provided employment; Akbar had ordered the construction of a fort and also recruited more soldiers in his army. He appointed Shaikh Farid Bukhari, who was a special famine officer while separate and free kitchens were established for Hindus, Muslims, and Jogis. Even during those times, a strong relationship could be seen between famines and unemployment. Thus, the relief measures that were adopted were in fact emergency measures which aimed to restore immediate entitlement for food through cash for work relief schemes.²⁴

The primary relief measure of providing employment at large public relief works was also aimed at generating income so that the minimum 'entitlement' to obtain food was protected. To ensure that the neediest to deserve relief should be selected, the government created a system of tests that were based on distance and residence along with the task work. These tests helped determine the need to alleviate the beneficiaries, which was given to them with maximum economy.

The tasks that were carried out by them were almost less than seventy-five percent of that which the labourers performed during normal times. In cases where they were capable of working, the wages earned for a day's work constituted only the entitlement

to state relief. Children aged six years also worked (carrying earth in baskets) in lieu of food by the state. Additionally, the needy had to trek long distances to reach the relief works. Permission was given for the construction of public works in Allahabad, Agra, and Bundelkhand divisions.²⁵

The Agra Commissioner was given Rs two thousand to start relief work for those who were capable. Later, relief work was also started at Farrukhabad, Mathura, and Kanpur. Initially, the number of people who applied for relief was manageable but soon it became an 'avalanche'.²⁶ By March 1838, over three lakh migrants had come to Agra from all over the Doab, even though the relief given was meagre. At Kanpur, only 800 of 5,000 applicants could be employed.²⁷ So, even though the demand for relief continued to increase, the cash sanctioned for the same remained very poor. There was a lot of pressure from district officers, but the Sudder Board refused to allocate more money. The paucity of funds was to such a large extent that in Agra there were not even enough tools and baskets for digging and carrying.²⁸ Also in Agra and Kanpur, the relief was provided only on alternate days.

Once the situation of famine was over, the affected people reverted back to traditional cultural norms. There was regret over breaking taboos and people atoned for their actions. The issue had also been given a lot of thought by *Brahmins*. They also declared that since the food taken in poor houses and relief centers was to save life, there would be no permanent loss of caste.

Thus, it is seen that even though the intent behind poor houses was to support and provide relief to the poor and needy, due to corruption and a non-empathetic attitude of the government and government officials, they were not very successful. But since the common man had no other alternative, despite the pathetic and deplorable conditions they availed the facility, especially the women and children.

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